

A High Sensitive Enzyme-Free H₂O₂ Sensor based on Prussian Blue Electrodeposition on Microporous-Au Electrode

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1 Introduction

Due to the extremely large specific surface areas for charge and mass transport in electrochemistry, three-dimensionally (3D) porous materials are important for both academic study and technological applications in batteries [1], sensors [2], and electronic materials [3].

Recently, a new green and promising template, gas bubble dynamic template, was proposed, by which self-supported 3D porous metals (Cu, Sn, Ag) and alloys (Cu₆Sn₅) with highly porous dendritic walls and numerous nanoparticles have been successfully prepared from electrochemical deposition processes[4],[5]. Chung *et.al* [2] prepared a non-enzyme glucose sensor by using this process subsequently annealing the microporous Cu to obtain microporous CuO for glucose determination.

Prussian blue (PB) is an inorganic compound with general formula is $KFe^{III}[Fe^{II}(CN)_6]$ or $Fe^{III}_4[Fe^{II}(CN)_6]_3$. PB is usually regarded as an “artificial enzyme peroxidase” because it has high activity and selectivity toward the reduction of H₂O₂ at a very low potential with a rapid catalytic rate [6]. Zhang *et.al* [7] fabricated a nanoporous gold electrode through alloying-dealloying approach, and then electrodeposited PB, this hydrogen peroxide sensor showed high sensitivity and outstanding repeatability and stability. However, the alloying-dealloying process will destroy the gold electrode.

Herein, we introduce a novel H₂O₂ sensor used the 3D microporous Au which synthesized by using hydrogen bubbles dynamic template, as a skeleton for the electrochemical deposition of PB and evaluated the performance of the resulting PB/microporous-Au modified electrode.

2 Experiments

CuSO₄, K₃[Fe(CN)₆], FeCl₃, HCl and 30% H₂O₂ were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. All the chemicals were analytical grade and used as received.

The gold electrode (area: 0.1 cm²) was polished and cleaned. The microporous-Au was successfully fabricated using the hydrogen bubbles dynamic template and followed by a galvanic replacement reaction between microporous-Cu and KAu(CN)₂. After that, the electrode was electrochemical dealloyed in H₂SO₄ and NaOH aqueous solution, respectively. [8]

PB was electrodeposited on microporous-Au electrode by using CV between -0.2 ~ 0.6 V. The electrolyte contained 25 mM FeCl₃, 2.5 mM K₃Fe(CN)₆, 0.1 M KCl and 0.1 M HCl. [7]

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Amperometric response of PB/microporous-Au modified electrode for H₂O₂ sensing

The amperometric responses of microporous-Au/PB modified electrode to successive additions of a certain amount of H₂O₂ at -0.05 V [9] in 20 mL pH 6.5 PBS under stirring was showed in Fig. 1a. The current was decreased rapidly after the addition of H₂O₂, and it can reach a stable state (95% of the maximum value) within 7 s, indicating a fast electron transfer rate between H₂O₂ and the modified electrode. Herein, the PB layer worked in here not only as a catalyst for H₂O₂ but also a charge transfer mediator. At the same time the porous structure of Au allowed rapid transport of liquid, and the extremely high surface area was desirable for electrochemical reactions. From the calibration curve for the amperometric response of the PPy microporous-Au/PB modified electrode (Fig. 1b), The modified electrode provided a linear response to H₂O₂ from 0.05 mM to 11.25 mM, with a correlation coefficient of 0.99975 and the sensitivity was 767 $\mu\text{A mM}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-2}$.

Fig. 1. (a) Current- time response of PB/microporous-Au modified electrode for successive addition of H_2O_2 in PBS at applied voltage was -0.05 V ; (b) calibration curve of current-concentration of H_2O_2 .

4 Conclusions

An electrochemical sensor for determination of hydrogen peroxide was fabricated by two electrodeposition steps. The Prussian blue modified microporous-Au electrode was used for determination of hydrogen peroxide using CA with a low applying potential. And the linear range for H_2O_2 concentration was from $50\ \mu\text{M}$ to $11.25\ \text{mM}$ with sensitivity of $767\ \mu\text{A}\ \text{mM}^{-1}\ \text{cm}^2$. The as-prepared PB/microporous-Au electrode showed excellent sensitivity and rapid response due to its larger surface area and rapid transport of liquid provided by 3D structure of microporous-Au.

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